

Author name disambiguation for fair representation of female scholars in science

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Abstract

Using bibliographic data, studies have reported that female scholars produce fewer papers and attract fewer citations than male scholars. These findings may be based on flawed data. As none of the existing bibliographic data services consolidates author entities with different last names, entities of female authors who change names are inevitably split into separate entities – one with a maiden name and the other with a marital name. This means that publications and citations of female authors who have used different names are likely undercounted, possibly leading to an under-evaluation of their scholarly productivity and impact. This study develops a machine learning method customized to consolidate female author entities in bibliographic data to promote fair representation and evaluation of women in science. This study creates large-scale labeled data to train algorithmic models to merge the same female author entities split under different names. It implements the models on author entities recorded in PubMed, which indexes research papers in biomedicine and demonstrates how the correct identification of name-changed female authors can lead us to a different understanding of research productivity and citation-based impact of female scholars in the field where almost half of the scientists are estimated to be female.

Introduction

Analyzing publication records, many studies reported that women tend to produce fewer papers and attract fewer citations than men in science (Long, 1992; Taylor et al., 2006), which is termed the ‘gender productivity gap’ in scholarly evaluation research. Although many related studies confirmed that women in science underperform in terms of scholarly productivity and impact, several studies counter-argued that no gender differences exist (Peñas & Willett, 2006; Van Arensbergen et al., 2012). In addition, some studies even claimed that female researchers tend to gather more citations than men (Long, 1992; Sandström, 2009).

Why does such a dispute over the gender productivity gap persist? The primary reason is that studies on the gender productivity gap tend to analyze small-sized, biased samples selected from a specific domain (*sampling issue*). For example, most studies on the topic relied on non-random samples of female and male researchers ranging between 45 and 440 (Astegiano et al., 2019). In addition, the sampled researchers worked in a few specialized fields, such as biochemistry, ecology, surgery, and social psychology, and their work time ranged between the early 1960s and 2000s. As such, many studies on the gender productivity gap were conducted as anecdotal case studies under different sampling conditions and variations, making it difficult for their claims to be compared for rigorous validation or generalization.

Unlike the sample-based studies, several studies used publication records ranging between a few thousand and a half million in size (Larivière et al., 2013; Lewison & Markusova, 2011). However, these studies used papers, not researchers, as a unit of analysis (*proxy issue*). They counted the appearances of female and male author names in each paper to measure productivity per gender. For impact measurement, they counted citations toward each paper and assigned them to each name (e.g., first, middle, and last) of each name. This proxy-based method has been used in more than 40 studies (Astegiano et al., 2019). However, the method cannot correctly represent the gender productivity gap as it does not consider how many unique researchers exist in the data analyzed.

In addition to the sampling and proxy issues, an entity identification problem contributes to the ongoing dispute (*entity issue*). This study argues that the findings of previous gender productivity gap studies are likely based on flawed data in which individual researchers are not adequately identified. Furthermore, female researchers are more unlikely to be correctly identified than male researchers. Specifically, female researchers may have changed their last names after marriage and have used the changed names in publications instead of their maiden names used in publications authored before marriage. A few of the 110 studies reviewed by Astegiano et al. (2019) acknowledged this entity disambiguation problem in their gathered data. However, only one small-sized sample study clarified that such a problem was addressed (Long, 1992). In large-scale proxy-based studies, the name change of female researchers is not considered, as most of these studies do not distinguish individual researchers.

Why does this entity issue matter for the gender productivity gap? Except for a few studies where a researcher's profile was manually curated based on CVs, most gender productivity gap studies have relied on publication records to measure productivity and impact. A problem with using publication records is that author names in the data can be ambiguous. For example, an author may have used a few name variations (e.g., Hispanic authors who use different combinations of surnames). Many authors may share the same name (e.g., Chinese authors with the same last and first names). So, suppose author names in publication records are not correctly disambiguated. In that case, studies can confuse several authors with the same name as a single researcher (entity merging error) and different names of a single author referring to multiple researchers (entity splitting error). Significantly, the latter error can be salient when female researchers change names during their careers. Thus, her entity is likely split into two entities – one with a maiden name and the other with a marital name. As most gender productivity gap studies used publication records where female author names are not correctly disambiguated, they are likely to under-count the number of papers authored by female researchers whose entities are split and, subsequently, the number of citations they receive for their papers. This means that women may be seen to underperform men in research production and impact purely due to an entity problem, while the gender productivity gap may or may not exist at all.

Significance of this study

To address the entity issue in the gender productivity gap research, this study is developing a machine learning method to correctly distinguish female researchers whose names appear in different name variations in publication records. The significance of this study can be explained in three ways. First, accurately identifying female and male researchers in publication records enables us to correctly count publications and citations per gender (the entity issue addressed). This disambiguation method applies to disambiguating author names recorded in large-scale bibliographic data that index journals and conferences in various scientific domains (the proxy issue addressed), thus enabling us to scrutinize and reconcile conflicting claims of previous studies about the gender productivity gap (the sampling issue addressed). Second, correctly understanding the gender productivity gap is crucial for the fair representation of women in science and effective policymaking on gender equity in science. Third, suppose the premise of previous studies that the gender productivity gap exists or is severe is changed by this study. In that case, research efforts can be directed more toward investigating the causes of gender discrimination, bias, and disparity in science. Figure 1 visualizes the core steps of this project.

Figure 1: Core Project Steps

Specific steps

Step #1: Creating large-scale labeled data to train algorithmic disambiguation models

Author name disambiguation using machine learning is recently gaining much attention in computer and information science. In algorithmic author name disambiguation, name instances are compared pairwise for their similarity to be decided for match or nonmatch. The number of matching pairs can increase quadratically in a worst-case scenario, increasing the computational burden considerably. So, blocking (i.e., comparing only names sharing a criterion) is conducted to reduce the number of matching pairs. A common practice in blocking is to collect names that share the first name initial and full surname. According to this blocking scheme, names with different surnames and first-name initials are not compared. Also, existing labeled data for author name disambiguation tend not to have labels for names with a different surname and first name initials but refer to the same authors. This means that current disambiguation methods and their labeled data cannot train algorithms to distinguish name instances of female scholars who use their changed surnames after marriage. A few studies mentioned that this issue could be problematic in women’s name disambiguation (Kim & Diesner, 2016; Strotmann & Zhao, 2012), but this study is the first to address the issue technically.

To create large-scale labeled data in which name instances of female researchers who change their last names are labeled, this study followed Kim and Owen-Smith (2021) to link publication records in ORCID that contain self-curated profiles of over 5 million researchers to 9 million publication records in PubMed through matching publication unique identifiers (e.g., DOI) and titles standard in both data. If a publication record was found to exist in both ORCID and PubMed, author names in the record were compared *token by token* to the name of the ORCID researcher who claims the paper’s ownership. If a matched token was found, the ORCID researcher’s unique id was assigned to the matched name in the paper as an author identification label. Using this linkage, this study could create labeled data of 3 million name instances from which large names that meet various sampling conditions can be drawn. This labeled data contained names of scholars who changed their names but maintained at least one token part of their name (e.g., first or middle name). A random sample of 3,400 author entities containing different surnames in publication records was selected for evaluation. A manual investigation of online profiles revealed that 92% of the selected entities are female, while the remaining are male (5%) or unknown for gender (3%). However, it is unknown whether this ORCID-linkage-based labeled data represent the researcher population regarding gender distribution. So, this study is also creating labeled data of 5,200 professors in computer science (male dominant), 800 in nursing (female dominant), and 1,100 in communication (balanced) to make labeled data approximate the gender composition in fields. For this, 19 students have worked on identifying gender and name change cases of professors in top U.S. research universities. However, broader coverage of fields is required to overcome the sample selection bias, which might require additional resources for creating representative labeled data.

Step #2: Implementing disambiguation models on author names in PubMed

PubMed is the world's largest digital library service that indexes papers in biomedicine. Its entire base data (MEDLINE) is annually released for non-restricted use. PubMed has been used in many bibliometrics studies to characterize research production, collaboration, and the impact of biomedical scholars worldwide. Also, it is reported that almost half of the research workforce in biomedicine are women (Rivers, 2017). So, this study uses PubMed (MEDLINE) to demonstrate the proposed disambiguation method.

Figure 2 shows the workflow of machine learning for disambiguation. Labeled data selected through stratified sampling from *Step #1* are split into training, development, and test sets. Pairs of name instances in the training set are compared for cosine similarity across features such as author name string, coauthor names, paper title, affiliation name, journal name, etc. Similarity scores calculated for positive (referring to the same authors) and negative (referring to different authors) pairs are fed into classifiers such as Random Forests and Gradient Boosting Trees which have been shown to perform best in many disambiguation studies (Levin et al., 2012; Santana et al., 2017) (classification stage). Also, name instances in development and test sets are compared for similarity over features by the same procedure applied to the training set. Then, disambiguation models of trained algorithms assign probability scores for the likelihood that two instances represent the same author in each pair in the development and test sets. Next, a hierarchical agglomerative clustering (HAC) algorithm collates name instances of a distinct author based on the pairwise probability scores (clustering stage). Here, a probability score between a pair of name instances represents a similarity distance between the pair. For the clustering stage, a mean probability score of blocks that maximizes the clustering performance evaluated on the development set is selected as a threshold value for HAC applied to the test set. This combination of classification and clustering has been shown to produce the best disambiguation results (Kim et al., 2021; Louppe et al., 2016; Torvik & Smalheiser, 2009; Vishnyakova et al., 2019).

Figure 2: Machine Learning Workflow for Disambiguation

The best model learned and validated from the machine learning procedure above is applied to PubMed. First, all name instances within the same blocks in PubMed are disambiguated through pairwise similarity comparison (instance-level disambiguation). The traditional blocking method (full surname + first forename initial) is used here. For this step, especially, HAC is fine-tuned to produce highly pure clusters (i.e., an author entity contains only names of the same author while a few names of the author may fail to be included). Next, the entities produced from the first step are disambiguated again through the aforementioned machine-learning procedure. Unlike instance-level disambiguation, however, labeled data are transformed into entity-level data (i.e., feature information aggregates per researcher), so algorithms learn how

to consolidate entities with different names. This time, entities are compared if they share a first forename token. Models trained and validated on the entity-level labeled data are then used for consolidating PubMed entities resulting from the instance-level disambiguation. Again, feature information of names in PubMed is aggregated per disambiguated entity to be consistent in format with the labeled data. The disambiguation accuracy will be assessed on several stratified samples from labeling results in *Step #1*.

Step #3: Demonstrating the impact of female author identification on fair representation

To illustrate the effect of the proposed disambiguation method on counts of research production and citation per gender, several steps of data filtering are conducted as follows. First, following previous studies on the gender productivity gap, a specialized field in biomedicine is selected (e.g., breast cancer). Then, disambiguated entities associated with five or more papers published in the journals in the selected field are collected. Among them, around 1,000 entities are randomly selected. Through manual inspection by two students, gender is verified and assigned for each entity. Then, the publication and citation of each entity are counted. Citation information (which paper cites which paper) is extracted by matching the publication id (PMID or PMCID) of a reference in a paper record to other papers' ids indexed in PubMed.

To create a baseline for comparison, all name instances of the selected 1,000 entities are disambiguated by a heuristic used in many gender productivity gap studies and bibliometrics research. Specifically, name instances with the same full name and first forename string are collected in a cluster (= an entity). Then, gender is assigned for each entity, and publication and citation are counted per entity as described above. Mean production and citation counts per gender can be compared under two different settings: one with entities produced by the proposed algorithmic method (with consolidated entities of female researchers) and another with entities produced by a common heuristic (with split entities of female researchers). This comparison will show us how different disambiguation methods lead to a different understanding of productivity and impact per gender. This comparison is repeated on samples drawn for other subfields indexed in PubMed.

Progress and expected outcome

Labeling in *Step #1* is completed, and its accuracy is under evaluation. The machine learning procedure in *Step #2* is now being implemented on MEDLINE. The findings derived from *Step #3* will enable the science community and policymakers to correctly characterize female scholars' research productivity and impact and implement adequate support and policies to promote fairness and equity for women in science. A tool that implements the newly developed method, the ORCID-linked labeled data (*Step #1*), and the disambiguated MEDLINE (*Step #2*) will be shared publicly for reuse, validation, and improvement.

Acknowledgments

This study is supported by the Michigan Institute of Data Science (MIDAS) Propelling Original Data Science (PODS) grant.

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